

**ÓZBEKSTAN RESPUBLIKASI JOQARI BILIMLENDIRIW, ILIM HÁM
INNOVACIYA MINISTRILIGI**

**ÓZBEKSTAN RESPUBLIKASI VETERINARIYA HÁM
SHARWASHÍLIQTÍ RAWAJLANDÍRÍW KOMITETI**

**SAMARQAND MÁMLEKETLIK VETERINARIYA MEDICINASI,
SHARWASHÍLIQ HÁM BIOTEKNOLOGIYALAR UNIVERSITETI
NÓKIS FILIALI**

**“ARALBOYÍ AYMAĞÍNDÁ SHARWASHÍLIQTA INNOVACION
TEKNOLOGIYALAR HÁM RAWAJLANDÍRÍWDÍN KELESHEGI”
atamasmdağı Respublikahq ilimiy-ámeliy konferenciya materiyalları
TOPLAMÍ
25-aprel 2025-jil**

**“OROL BO‘YI HUDUDIDA CHORVACHILIKDA INNOVATSION
TEKNOLOGIYALAR VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLARI”
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«Aralboyı aymağında sharwashılıqta innovacion texnologiyalar hám rawajlandırıwdıń keleshegi» atamasındaǵı Respublikalıq ilimiy hám ilimiy-texnikalıq konferenciya materialları: toplam // Samarqand mámleketlik veterinariya medicinası, sharwashılıq hám biotexnologiyalar universiteti Nókis filialı. Nókis, 2025 jıl.-245 b.

Bul konferenciya Ózbekstan Respublikası Joqarı bilimlendiriw, ilim hám innovaciyaqar ministrliginiń 2024-jıl 27-dekabrdegi “2025-jılda xalıq aralıq hám respublikalıq kólemindegi ótkeriletuǵın ilimiy hám ilimiy-texnikalıq ilajların tastıyıqlaw haqqında”ǵı 490-sanlı buyırǵına muwapıq ótkizildi.

Toplam materiallarınan veterinariya hám sharwashılıq tarawındaǵı JOO hám ilimiy izertlew institutlarında ilimiy-izertlewler alıp barıp atırǵan professor-oqıtıwshılar, jas ilimpazlar, doktorantlar, erkin izleniwshiler, magistrantlar hám ziyrek talabalar paydalanıwı múmkin.

Toplam: Samarqand mámleketlik veterinariya medicinası, sharwashılıq hám biotexnologiyalar universiteti Nókis filialı Keńesi tárepinen baspadan shıǵarıwǵa usınılǵan.

Esletpe: Konferenciya materialları toplamǵa kiritilgen maqalalardıń mazmunı ushın baspaxana hám shólkemlestiriwshi komitet juwapker emes. Maqalalar avtorlar tárepinen keltirilgen maǵlıwmatlar tiykarında baspadan shıǵarıldı.

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SÓZ BASI

Songı jıllarda mámleketimizde awıl xojalıǵı, ásirese veterinariya hám sharwashılıq tarawların rawajlandırıwǵa joqarı itibar qaratılmaqta. Bul rawajlanıwlar óz gezeginde tarawdaǵı ónimdarlıqtı asırıwǵa, zamanagóy ilimiy-innovacion nátiyjelerdi óndiriske engizilip kelmekte.

Sharwashılıqtı intensiv rawajlandırıw, xalqımızdı sıpatlı gósh, sút hám basqada azıq awqat ónimleri menen támiynlew házirgi kúnniń aktual mashqalası esaplanadı. Ózbekistan Respublikası Prezidenti Sh.M. Mirziyoyevtiń 2019-jıl 18-marttaǵı PQ-4243-sanlı qararı, Ózbekistan Respublikası Prezidentiniń 2020-jıl 29-yanvardaǵı PQ-45-76-sanlı – Sharwashılıq tarawın mámleket tárepinen qollap-quwatlawdıń qospa is-ilajları haqqındaǵı qararına tiykarlanıp sharwashılıq tarawların jedel rawajlandırıw, zamanagóy hám innovacion usılların ámeliyatqa engiziw, ónimlerdi islep shıǵarıw kólemin asırıw hám túrlerin kóbeytiw, sonday-aq, xalıqtı jergilikli jaǵdayda islep shıǵarıwǵan sıpatlı hám arzan sharwa ónimleri menen úzliksiz támiynlew hámde sharwashılıqqa qánigelestirilgen kárxanalardı mámleket tárepinen qollap-quwatlaw maqsetinde, búgingi kúnde mámleketimizde xalıq xojlalıǵınıń barlıq tarawlarında ekonomikalıq, shólkemlestiriw, sotsiyallıq hám siyasiy tárepten tereń reformalar dawam etpekte. Bul usı tarawda jumıs islep atırǵan barlıq sharwa qánigelerine úlken juwapkeshilik júkleydi.

Sharwashılıq – bul tek ǵana ekonomikalıq taraw emes, bálki xalıqtıń turmıs dárejesin asırıw, awıllarda jumıs orınların jaratıw, azıq-awqat qawipsizligin támiynlew, sonıń menen birge, milliy ónimlerimizdi ishki hám sırtqı bazarlarda básekige shıdamlı etiwge xızmet etiwshi taraw bolıp tabıladı.

Usı konferenciyaǵa kiritilgen ilimiy maqalalar hám ilimiy-izertlewler dúnya iliminiń jańa jetiskenliklerin óz ishine alǵan halda, jergilikli shárayatqa maslasqan ilimiy nátiyjelerdi usınıs etedi.

Bul konferenciya joqarı oqıw orınlarınıń ilimiy potencialın asırıw, veterinariya hám sharwashılıq tarawında birge islesiwdi jolǵa qoyıw, ilimiy-izertlew jumısların jedellestiriw, ilim hám islep shıǵarıw integraciyasın kúsheytiw, professor-oqıtıwshılar quramınıń ilimiy jumıslarınıń nátiyjeliligin asırıw, sonıń menen birge, ziyrek talabalar, magistrantlar hám doktorantlardı ilimiy-izertlew jumıslarına tartıwda ayırıqsha áhmiyetke iye.

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CULTIVATION OF HALOPHYTE PLANTS

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In recent years, the cultivation of halophyte plants has gained significant attention due to their ability to thrive in saline environments. With the increasing salinization of agricultural lands worldwide, halophytes offer a promising alternative for sustainable agriculture. Moreover, these plants contribute to soil reclamation, biofuel production, and food security. This article explores the characteristics, benefits, cultivation techniques, and economic significance of halophyte plants. Additionally, it discusses historical uses, current research, and potential future developments in the field of halophyte farming

Characteristics of Halophyte Plants Halophyte plants possess unique adaptations that enable them to thrive in high-salinity environments where most conventional crops would fail. A key characteristic of halophytes is salt tolerance. Some species have salt-excreting glands to remove excess salt, while others store it in vacuoles to maintain osmotic balance. Additionally, they exhibit drought resistance, with deep root systems and succulent leaves that help retain moisture and reduce water loss. Halophytes are highly adaptable, thriving in diverse conditions such as coastal marshes, salt flats, and saline deserts. Some species even withstand fluctuating salinity levels, making them useful for soil reclamation. Furthermore, their extensive root systems help stabilize soil, prevent erosion, and protect shorelines from storm surges. Overall, halophytes play a

crucial role in sustainable agriculture, environmental conservation, and commercial applications such as biofuel production and pharmaceuticals

Historical and Traditional Uses of Halophytes. Historically, halophytes have been utilized in various cultures for their medicinal, culinary, and ecological benefits. Coastal communities have long harvested edible halophytes such as *Salicornia* and sea purslane for their high nutritional value. In traditional medicine, certain halophyte species have been used to treat ailments such as skin conditions, digestive disorders, and inflammation. Additionally, in arid regions, halophytes have been employed for soil stabilization, preventing desertification and improving agricultural productivity.

Benefits of Halophyte Cultivation. The cultivation of halophytes offers numerous environmental, agricultural, and economic benefits, making them a sustainable alternative in regions affected by soil salinization and water scarcity. Halophytes absorb excess salts from the soil, helping to reduce salinity levels and restore degraded lands. This makes them useful for reclaiming abandoned farmlands and improving soil structure, which is particularly beneficial in arid and semi-arid regions. Many halophytes, such as *Salicornia* and *Atriplex*, are nutrient-rich edible plants that can supplement human diets. Additionally, they serve as fodder for livestock, providing a sustainable feed option in saline environments where conventional forage crops fail. Certain halophytes, such as *Salicornia* and *Spartina*, contain high levels of oil and biomass, making them a promising feedstock for biofuel production. This reduces reliance on fossil fuels and supports the development of renewable energy sources. Unlike traditional crops that require freshwater, halophytes can be irrigated with saline or brackish water, reducing pressure on freshwater resources. This is particularly advantageous in coastal and drought-prone areas. Halophytes play a crucial role in carbon sequestration, absorbing atmospheric CO₂ and helping to combat climate change. Some species, like mangrove-associated halophytes, also protect coastal areas from erosion and rising sea levels. Halophyte-based industries, including food production, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and biofuels, are expanding, creating new economic opportunities for farmers and businesses. The increasing global interest in sustainable agriculture further enhances the market potential of halophyte-derived products. Halophyte cultivation offers a sustainable solution for saline agriculture, food security, and environmental conservation. With continued research and investment, these plants could play a vital role in addressing global agricultural and ecological challenges [3, 118-120]

Techniques for Halophyte Cultivation. The successful cultivation of halophytes requires specialized techniques to optimize their growth in saline environments. These techniques include soil management, irrigation strategies, plant selection, and integrated farming systems.

1. Selection of Suitable Halophyte Species Different halophyte species thrive under varying levels of salinity, temperature, and soil conditions. Selecting the right species, such as *Salicornia*, *Atriplex*, and *Spartina*, based on regional environmental factors ensures better growth and productivity.

2. Soil and Land Preparation-Salinity Assessment: Testing soil salinity levels helps determine the most appropriate halophyte species.-Soil Amendment: Organic matter and gypsum can be added to improve soil fertility and structure.-Raised Beds and Mulching: These techniques help manage water retention and salt accumulation, reducing stress on plants

3. Drip Irrigation: Delivers controlled amounts of saline water directly to plant roots, minimizing salt buildup.-Tidal Irrigation: Utilized in coastal farming, allowing seawater to nourish halophytes without excessive salt accumulation.-Sequential Irrigation: Alternates between freshwater and saline water to prevent excessive salt concentration in the soil.

4. Agroforestry and Integrated Farming-Halophyte-Aquaculture Systems: Combining halophyte farming with fish or shrimp cultivation helps recycle nutrients and optimize water use.-Intercropping with Conventional Crops: Some halophytes can be grown alongside salt-tolerant crops to improve soil quality and enhance agricultural biodiversity.

5. Genetic Improvement and Biotechnology Advancements in plant breeding and genetic engineering are enhancing the salt tolerance and yield of halophytes, making them more viable for large-scale agricultural production.

The cultivation of halophytes using innovative soil, water, and farming techniques presents a sustainable solution for food security, environmental conservation, and economic development in saline-affected regions

Challenges and Future Prospects of Halophyte Cultivation. Despite its benefits, large-scale halophyte cultivation faces challenges. Limited awareness and research hinder adoption, as many farmers remain uncertain about market demand and profitability. Additionally, while halophytes thrive in saline environments, specific soil conditions and irrigation are needed for optimal yields, requiring costly infrastructure investments. Climate change further complicates halophyte farming, as rising sea levels and shifting precipitation patterns may affect growth. However, advancements in genetics, biotechnology, and microbial inoculants offer promising solutions to enhance salt tolerance and productivity. Policy support and investment are crucial for widespread adoption. Governments and environmental organizations recognize halophytes' role in combating desertification and ensuring food security. Integrating them into sustainable agriculture policies can help mitigate soil salinization and water scarcity [6, 144-153].

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MINERAL AGRORUDALARNING KUZGI BUG'DOY O'SISHI VA RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotaciya: Mavzu hozirgi kunda respublika dehqonchiligida dolzrab bo'lganligi sababali ilmiy tadqiqotlarning ustivor yo'nalishlariga mos keladi mazkur tadqiqotlar yakunlangandan so'ng tuproq unumdorligini va kuzgi bug'doy hosildorligini oshiruvchi o'tmishdosh ekinlar Qoraqalpog'iston sharoitida birinchi marotaba aniqlanadi.

Tuproq sho'rlanishini kamaytirish, tuproq unumdorligi va ekinlar hosildorligi va sifatini oshirish uchun agromeliorativ tadbirlarni olib borish, o'tmishdosh ekinlar va mineral agrorudalarning kuzgi bug'doy hosildorligini oshirishdagi samaradorligini ishlab chiqish, erga organik va siderat o'g'itlarni qo'llash - muammolarini hal qilish yo'li deb hisoblaymiz.

Kalit so'z: Kuzgi bug'doy, tuproq, unumdorlik, mineral agroruda, glaukanit, o'tmishdosh, hosildorlik.

Kirish. Kuzgi bug'doy biologik xususiyatlariga kura kuzgi ekin bo'lganligi sababli qishqi sovuqlarning salbiy ta'siriga chidamli bo'lishi kerak. Biroq mamlakatimiz iqlimi keskin kontinental (yozi issiq kishi sovuq) bo'lishiga qaramasdan kuz, qish va bahor kezlarida ob-havo juda tez uzgaruvchanligi va ayrim agrotexnologik jarayonlarning noto'g'ri qo'llanilishi oqibatida qishqi sovuqlar ta'sirida nobud bo'lishi yoki siyraklashish holatlari ko'rsatiladi. Shuning uchun ham kuzgi bug'doyni qishqi sovuqlarning salbiy ta'siridan asirash ishlari urug'ni ekish bilan birga boshlanishi kerak. Ekinni kishki sovuqlarning salbiy ta'siridan asrash uchun avvalo qishqi sovuqlarga chidamli tez pishar navlarini tanlash maqbul muddatlarda tegishli me'yorlarda ekish va to'g'ri oziqlantirish